

PROCESSES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF THERMAL INSULATION BOARDS BASED ON LOCAL RAW MATERIALS.

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Annotation: *In this article, the processes of making heat-insulating plates based on local raw materials were studied.*

Key words: *plastic strength, bending strength, straw, liquid glass, rock, mineral binder, thermal insulation board.*

In recent years, many studies have been conducted on the construction of energy-efficient, heat-saving ecological houses from plate materials based on organic fillers and mineral binders [1, 2].

Such heat-insulating plates used in buildings embody a number of properties of organic filler and mineral binder.

Nowadays, heat-insulating plates are sold in different countries of the world - Germany, England, the Netherlands, Japan, etc. is being produced. Wastes from agriculture and woodworking enterprises are mainly used in their production (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. From heat-insulating plates of the German company "Bison".
ready-made 1-story prefabricated building

Due to the fact that wood is mainly imported to the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the volume of waste generated in woodworking enterprises cannot be used to produce heat insulating materials based on organic fillers and mineral binders in sufficient quantities for construction needs.

However, it should also be noted that there is a large amount of agricultural waste (stalks, straw, rice husks, etc.) in the territory of the republic.

If the production of products from these wastes is started, great benefits will be seen both ecologically and economically. At the same time, the construction sector is also provided with necessary materials.

Houses built from materials based on mineral binders and organic fillers are of great importance in world practice. If we compare them with houses made of wood, their lifespan increases due to the loss of conditions for the development of pests, the formation of mold and the growth of fungi.

Research objects and results

To obtain heat-insulating materials, the following were used as the main components:

- crushed straw: straw stem length 30-50 mm, diameter 2-4 mm;
- steel scrap of the Bekobod metallurgical plant (table 1);
- liquid glass (low-modulus and high-modulus - aqueous solutions of sodium silicate differing in viscosity, silicate modulus and density) [3].

More than 100,000 tons of steel ore is produced at this plant every year. Today, these stones are piled up to 2 million. accumulated in tons [4].

The possibility of using Bekobod metallurgical stone as an additive in cement production has been studied by field scientists.

Also, before using the steel scrap, it is necessary to recycle the metal scraps in it.

The chemical composition of Bekobod metallurgical plant steel rock is presented in Table 1.

The steel scrap of the metal smelting shop of the Bekobod metallurgical plant is produced in the production of different grades of steel.

Its distinctive features are that they contain up to 20% iron oxides.

Chemical composition of Bekobod metallurgical plant steel ore

Table 1

Name	Composition of oxides, %								
	iO ₂	aO	l ₂ O ₃	eO	e ₂ O ₃	gO	nO	2O ₅	The rest
Bekobod metallurgical plant steel mill	8,6	1,9	0,6	5	0,5	2	0,9	0,9	Other substances

The composition of steel rock mainly consists of the following minerals: monticellite (CMS) d=4.19, 2.66, 3.63, 2.94 A, braunmillerite (CnAF) d=2.77, 2.63, 2.19, 2.03, 1.92 A, ferrite phase (C2F) d=2.66 , 2.52, 2.11 A, quartz (SiO2) d=4.24, 3.34, 2.45 A, etc. The steel was crushed in a ball mill and used as a powder with a fineness of 300 m²/kg on a PSX-2 device.

In our research, mineral binders based on steel rock and liquid glass were obtained and their properties were studied.

Properties of mineral binders are presented in Table 2.

Properties of mineral binders

Table 2

Steel rock	Liquid glass density,kg/m	Hardening time (start-end),	Compressive strength after 28
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		3	minutes	days, MPa
	100 %	1300	7-16	33

In our further research, the hardening process of samples prepared from a mixture of mineral binder and organic filler was studied.

In conducting this experiment, we used a new method, that is, we evaluated the hardening of the samples by changing its plastic strength (P_m). In this case, the plastic strength was determined by the "Höppler" consistometer developed by the scientists of the Institute of "General and Inorganic Chemistry" of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

In the conducted experiments, the solidification of samples prepared on the basis of liquid glasses of different modules under normal conditions was studied. In this case, liquid glass with a density of 1200, 1300 and 1400 kg/m³ was used.

The obtained experimental results are presented in Table 3.

**Made on the basis of liquid bottles of different modules
hardening of mineral binders under normal conditions**

Table 3

	Composition of samples	Plastic strength (P_m), kg/sm ²						
		min	5 min	0 min	hour	hour	hour	hour
.	Stone; Liquid bottle ($\rho=1200$ kg/m ³).	0,4	0,6	0,0	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8
.	Stone; Liquid bottle ($\rho=1300$ kg/m ³).	0,8	0,1	0,6	0,8	0,8	0,4	0,4
.	Stone; Liquid bottle ($\rho=1400$ kg/m ³).	0,0	0,2	0,8	0,0	0,3	0,1	4,3

The obtained experimental results revealed that the plastic strength of samples 1, 2 and 3 increases with the increase in density of liquid glass (from 1200 to 1400 kg/m³). However, the initial plastic strength of the samples is very small. The solidification process of the samples accelerates intensively only after 1 hour. The plastic strength of samples 1, 2, and 3 hardened for 6 hours is 8.8, 9.4, and 14.3 kg/sm², respectively.

It can be seen that the solidification process of samples accelerates as the density of liquid glass increases.

In our further research, in order to determine the alternative composition of samples made from a mixture of mineral binder and organic filler, research was conducted to study the effect of a number of factors - the amount and density of liquid glass on the plate properties.

In the conducted experiments, the static bending strength of heat-insulating plates was determined.

The plate preparation was carried out based on the following technology: crushed straw, liquid glass and crushed stone were mixed until a homogeneous mass was formed; the prepared mixture was placed in a mold and compacted at a pressure of 3.5 MPa; processed in hot-humid conditions; then the plate is held under normal conditions for strengthening; finally the solidified slab was dried and tested.

In the experiment, the amount of liquid glass was increased from 20 to 40%, respectively, compared to the amount of stone.

The results of the experiment are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Heat insulating material durability depending on the amount of liquid glass

1 - 1400 kg/m³ sample based on liquid glass of density

2 - 1200 kg/m³ sample based on liquid glass of density

As it can be seen from the obtained experimental results, an increase in the amount of liquid glass in the composition up to 30% leads to an intensive increase in the static bending strength of the plate. This is explained by the fact that the surface of the straw filler is sufficiently covered with filled stones and liquid glass.

As can be seen from Figure 2, increasing the amount of liquid glass after 30% does not significantly affect the bending strength of the plate. Therefore, 30% was accepted as the optimal amount.

Summary

As a result of the conducted research, the processes of obtaining heat-insulating plates based on local raw materials were analyzed. The hardening process of mineral binder based on steel stone and liquid glass was studied. Also, the optimal amount of liquid glass for heat-insulating plates based on steel straw and liquid glass was determined.

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